

1. Dry matter yield and grain yield of 57 F₁ hybrids and 43 inbreds with different growth durations, IRRI, 1988 dry season. Vertical lines represent the standard error of the mean.

2. Harvest index of F₁ hybrids and inbreds with different growth durations, IRRI, 1988 DS. Vertical lines represent the standard error of the mean.

slightly lower yield by very short-duration entries. F₁ hybrids and inbreds with growth durations of 125-129 d had the highest grain yield.

The increase in biomass with growth duration and the almost constant grain yield regardless of growth duration resulted in higher HI in short-duration

cultivars (Fig. 2). F₁ hybrids showed an average 10% advantage in HI over inbreds. (HI higher than 0.50 is often observed in short-duration F₁ hybrids.)

F₁ hybrids, regardless of duration, showed heterosis for total dry weight production and HI, with greatly increased grain yields. □

Effect of stem thickness and carbohydrate content on ratoon rice yield

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We studied the effect of stem thickness and carbohydrate content on yield of ratoon rice in 1984-85 and 1985-86. Varieties were Bhavani, Ponni, and IR20, in a randomized block design with three replications. The main crops were cultivated according to recommended practices.

Stem thickness of the ratoons was measured with a screw-gauge at harvest of the main crop. Carbohydrate content of the stubble was estimated immediately after harvest by the method suggested by Somogyi, using the Spectronic-20 colorimeter.

In both years, Bhavani had significantly higher ratoon crop grain yield (see table). Its stem thickness was also significantly higher than that of the two other varieties. Bhavani also had the highest carbohydrate content in the stubble. This could have induced more vigorous regeneration of ratoon tillers, resulting in the production of a larger number of tillers and higher grain yield. □

Stem thickness, carbohydrate content, and ratoon rice yield.

Variety	1984-85			1985-86		
	Stem thickness (mm)	Carbohydrate content (%)	Ratoon grain yield (t/ha)	Stem thickness (mm)	Carbohydrate content (%)	Ratoon grain yield (t/ha)
Bhavani	3.5	8.9	1.6	3.1	8.8	2.9
Ponni	2.8	7.8	1.0	2.7	7.9	1.3
IR20	2.8	7.6	0.3	2.8	7.6	0.3
LSD (0.05)	0.5	0.4	0.1	0.1	0.7	0.2

Variation in rice hull weights

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One way to further improve rice yields in the tropics is to increase the harvest index (HI) — the ratio of grain weight to biomass. (Wheat shows higher HI than rice, whose hull weight is substantially heavier than wheat chaff.) Reducing the partitioning of dry weight to the hull could be an approach to improving HI.

We examined seasonal variations in hull weight. Early-maturing IR58 and medium-maturing IR29723-143-3-2-1 were transplanted each month for 1 yr. Spacing was 20 × 20 cm, fertilizer was 120 kg N/ha. Filled grains (1.06 specific gravity) of each harvest were separated by salt solution and dried at 80°C for 5 d. Three 200-seed samples per transplanting month were dehulled manually, redried for 24 h, and hull and kernel weight determined. Grains of 10 different cultivars were dehulled for comparison.

Seasonal variation in kernel and hull weight of IR29723-143-3-2-1 in the monthly planting experiment. IIRRI, 1989.

In IR29723-143-3-2-1, hull and kernel weight varied remarkably with transplanting date (see figure). The trend with IR58 was similar. Hull weights of grain harvested from Sep to Nov were higher than those of grain harvested in other months. Kernel weight variations were similar to those of hull weight. Thus, the hull weight ratio (HWR—hull weight divided by grain weight) was almost constant through the year. This means that HWR could be a useful, stable indicator in screening for cultivars with lower hull weight.

Varietal difference in hull weight ratio (hull weight/grain weight). IIRRI, 1989.

Cultivar	Hull weight ratio ^a
Binato	0.26 ± 0.005
Peta	0.28 ± 0.002
IR8	0.29 ± 0.002
IR32	0.28 ± 0.002
IR58	0.30 ± 0.002
IR64	0.27 ± 0.008
IR65	0.28 ± 0.007
IR54752B	0.32 ± 0.004
IR25588-7-3-1	0.25 ± 0.001
IR29723-143-3-2-1	0.23 ± 0.002

^aA_v = 0.28.

Clear differences in HWR were found in the 10 cultivars compared (see table). (The lowest HWR found was still much higher than the ratio of wheat chaff weight to total grain weight.)

Seasonal and varietal differences in hull weights suggest the possibility of breeding rice with a lower HWR. It would be worthwhile to examine the extent of HWR variation in rice and to determine its heritability. ■

Computer simulation of the potential production of rice

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The MACROS model simulates physiological and physical processes by which meteorological variables affect the growth and development of rice. Crop parameters, weather variables, and management factors are inputs in the model. Values of state variables, such as the weights of different plant organs, and of rate variables, such as photosynthetic rate, are computed progressively for each day of the growing season.

We used MACROS to calculate potential production of rice crops.

The model was evaluated using data from 1986 and 1987 dry season experi-

ments on growth of rice cultivar IR64 and breeding line IR29723-143-3-2-1. It gave reasonable estimates of the weights of different plant organs (Fig. 1). However, it requires accurate values of initial weights. Simulated canopy photosynthesis agreed well with measured canopy photosynthesis.

Appropriate submodels were selected and MACROS was used to simulate potential grain yields in four situations: IR64 and IR36 in fully irrigated conditions, IR64 transplanted in rainfed lowland, and Kinandang Pula (KP) dry seeded in rainfed upland. The model was run for crops transplanted at weekly intervals for 27 yr (1960-88), and 10, 25, 75, and 90% cumulative probability yield levels for specific flowering dates computed (Fig. 2).

Yield was most strongly related to flowering date because weather

1. Simulated and observed dry matter of different plant organs. Data for IR64 obtained from IIRRI Plant Physiology Department, 1986 dry season. F = observed date of flowering, M = observed date of maturity.